

THE ROLE OF THE PROJECT- BASED LEARNING FOR STUDENTS.

Mamatqulova Gulnigorbonu Barxayot kizi

master's student in the field of "Management of educational institutions" in the faculty Pedagogy
of Chirchik State of Pedagogical University

E-mail: maxameru2001@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927360>

Abstract. *The article examines improving the quality of lessons and using the "Project-based learning" method and its important aspects in order to improve effectiveness of education process.*

Keywords: *creative thinking, pedagogical forms, national program, teaching-methodical manuals and exercise books, project work.*

The government of Uzbekistan have always been trying to support the youth, give them a chance to develop, raise. Year by year the conditions of living are rising, the mind and knowledge of the citizens are becoming wider. Especially, after gaining independence there were created a lot of opportunities for people; appeared new ways of communicating with foreign countries, to make business, to study. This demanded from the people to learn foreign languages. As English is spoken around the world, the person who wants to work with foreigners needs to master this language.

In general, students play a leading role in the interactive method of teaching, which is determined by their excellent command of a foreign language, the ability to express themselves independently, that is, the ability to speak fluently. Project-based learning (PBL) or project-based instruction is an instructional approach designed to give students the opportunity to develop knowledge and skills through engaging projects set around challenges and problems they may face in the real world. Project Work-Based Learning gives a thorough practical exposure to a problem upon which the project is based. Projects are developed generally in groups where students can learn various things such as working together, problem-solving, decision making, and investigating activities.

Project work enables the students to develop an inquisitive mind, always wanting to find out why things happens the way they happen. The usefulness of project work is that it enables the student to be methodical in his approach to solving the research problem.

For instance, have your students work together to create a mural. They will work to conceptualize the mural, design it, plan it, and then paint it. Art projects provide opportunities for your students to express their creativity and work together as a team.

Essential Project Design Elements

Content knowledge and conceptual understanding, by themselves, are not enough in today's world. In school and college, in the modern workplace, as citizens and in their lives generally, people need to be able to think critically and solve problems, work well with others, and communicate effectively. We could add other skills to the list, such as creativity/innovation and project management. We call these kinds of competencies "success skills." They are also known as "21st Century Skills" or "College and Career Readiness Skills" and are often seen in "Graduate Profiles" created by schools and districts.

It's important to note that success skills can only be taught through the acquisition of content knowledge and understanding. For example, students don't learn critical thinking skills in the abstract, isolated from subject matter; they gain them by thinking critically about math, science, history, English, career/tech subjects, the arts, and so on. Projects may also help build habits of mind and work and personal qualities (such as perseverance, growth mindset, or compassion), based on what teachers, schools, parents and communities value.

High quality student work is a hallmark of Gold Standard PBL, and such quality is attained through thoughtful critique and revision. Students should be taught how to give and receive constructive peer feedback that will improve project processes and products, guided by rubrics, models, and formal feedback/critique protocols. In addition to peers and teachers, outside adults and experts can also contribute to the critique process, bringing an authentic, real-world point of view. This common-sense acknowledgement of the importance of making student work and student products better is supported by research on the importance of "formative evaluation," which not only means teachers giving feedback to students, but students evaluating the results of their learning.

Project based learning offers some benefits in teaching and learning process which include giving contextual and meaningful learning for students, creating optimal environment to practice speaking English, engaging students actively in project learning, enhancing the students' interest, motivation, engagement.

So, it can be concluded that, the main idea behind project work is to make sure that the learner does their own research and comes up with practical solutions to the concept they are trying to learn or the problem that they are trying to solve. Project-based learning is an opportunity for students to critique and revise their approach when they encounter obstacles. As they continue to actively explore a real-world problem, they acquire a deeper knowledge that requires further inquiry "they have to keep going."

REFERENCES

1. Ahmedova, L., T., Normuratova, V. I., Teaching English Practicum. (2011)
2. Allen, L., Q. (2004). Implementing a culture portfolio project within a constructivist paradigm. *Foreign Language Annals*.
3. Brinia, V. (2006). Experiential learning in the subject □ Organisation and business administration □ in general upper secondary school: A suggestion for effective education.
4. Brophy, J. (2004). *Motivating Students to Learn*. New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates. Brophy, J., & Alleman, J. (2000). Activities as instructional tools: A framework for analysis and evaluation. *Educational Researcher*.
5. Coleman, J. A. (2000). Project-based learning, transferable skills, information technology and video. *Language Learning Journal*.
6. Crisafidis, K. (2005). Experiential-communicative teaching. Implementing the project method in school. Athens: Gutenberg. (in Greek).
7. Deci, E., L., & Moller, A., C. (2005). The concept of competence: A starting place for understanding intrinsic motivation and self-determined extrinsic motivation. In A. J. Elliot & C. S. Dweck (Eds.), *Handbook of competence and motivation* (pp. 579-597). New York: Guildford Press.
8. www.ziyonet.uz
9. www.referaat.com
10. www.antithestsigeogte.com
11. www.wikipedia.com
12. http://www.hi-edu.ru/e-books/xbook_107/01/part-195.htm
13. <http://www.lep.utm.edu/conc-cl>.
14. www.researchgate.net